

Generalist Repository Comparison Chart

This chart is designed to assist researchers in finding a generalist repository should no domain repository be available to preserve their research data. Generalist repositories accept data regardless of data type, format, content, or disciplinary focus. For this chart, we included a repository available to all researchers specific to clinical trials (Vivli) to bring awareness to those in this field.

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TOPIC	DATVERSE (HARVARD DATVERSE REPOSITORY)	DRYAD	FIGSHARE	MENDELEY	OSF	VIVLI	ZENODO
Brief Description	The Harvard Dataverse Repository , the endowed permanent data sharing repository of Harvard University, is a managed data repository open to all researchers from any discipline, both inside and outside of the Harvard community, where you can share, archive, cite, access, and explore research data. Powered by The Dataverse Project, the repository was released in 2006 by the Institute for Quantitative Social Science (IQSS) at Harvard University and is one of the largest repositories of open research data in the world, hosting thousands of datasets across a wide range of disciplines. The repository is free and open to the research community for data sharing and is supported by Harvard Library and Harvard University Information Technology.	Dryad is a non-profit, open-source publishing platform committed to the open sharing and reuse of data in all fields of research. All Dryad datasets are thoroughly evaluated by a team of experienced curators prior to publication.	Figshare is a freely available open data publishing platform where researchers can FAIR-ly share and get credit for all outputs of their scholarly work including any file type from any research discipline and larger datasets via Figshare Plus.	Mendeley Data is a free generalist repository specialized for research data. Search more than 20+ million datasets indexed from 1000s of data repositories and collect and share datasets with the research community following the FAIR data principles.	OSF is a free and open source project management and collaboration tool that supports researchers throughout their entire project lifecycle in open science best practices.	Vivli is an independent, non-profit organization that has developed a global data-sharing and analytics platform. Our focus is on sharing individual participant-level data from completed clinical trials to serve the international research community.	Zenodo is a general-purpose repository for all digital research outputs operated by CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research) and funded by the European Commission, the National Institutes of Health in the United States, the Arcadia Foundation, and the Sloan Foundation. Zenodo is noncommercial and based fully on the InvenioRDM open source repository platform.
Operated By	The Dataverse Project	Dryad	Digital Science	Elsevier	Center for Open Science (COS)	Vivli	CERN

TOPIC	DATAVERSE (HARVARD DATAVERSE REPOSITORY)	DRYAD	FIGSHARE	MENDELEY	OSF	VIVLI	ZENODO
Data Storage, Sharing, Access, and Preservation							
Costs to the Researcher	<p>Deposit Fee: Free up to 1TB, Free for Harvard affiliates up to 2.5TB</p> <p>Curation Service & Support: Paid Curation Services available</p> <p>Increased Storage: For larger collections and datasets, Harvard Repository offers additional paid storage options.</p> <p>Research Environment: N/A</p> <p>Independent Review Panel: N/A</p>	<p>Deposit Fee: 150 USD per published data package</p> <p>Some institutions and journals will cover the publication fee on the author's behalf through their membership with Dryad.</p> <p>Fee waivers for data publication are available upon approval of application.</p> <p>More information about Dryad data publication charges is available here.</p> <p>Curation Service & Support: Free curation and dedicated support provided by Dryad's experienced data curators and Help Desk.</p> <p>Increased Storage: For datasets exceeding 300GB, Dryad will work directly with authors to upload their large data package. Dryad charges excess storage fees for data totaling over 50GB. For more information about large data charges is available here.</p> <p>Research Environment: N/A</p> <p>Independent Review Panel: N/A</p>	<p>Deposit Fee: None</p> <p>Curation Service & Support: Available for large datasets through Figshare Plus (see below)</p> <p>Increased Storage: Figshare Plus offers additional storage as well as dataset review for a one-time data publishing fee based on total storage.</p> <p>Research Environment: N/A</p> <p>Independent Review Panel: N/A</p>	<p>Deposit Fee: None</p> <p>Curation Service & Support: Free</p> <p>Increased Storage: Available, along with Projects and Collections via commercial institutional offering Digital Commons Data</p> <p>Research Environment: N/A</p> <p>Independent Review Panel: N/A</p>	<p>Deposit Fee: None</p> <p>Curation Service & Support: Yes, community operated services with moderation, curation, and insights features are available.</p> <p>Increased Storage: See fees; OSF Institutional member affiliates receive 2x storage at no additional cost.</p> <p>Research Environment: N/A</p> <p>Independent Review Panel: N/A</p>	<p>Deposit Fee: None, if your institution is a member of Vivli. If your academic institution is not a member, there is a one-time cost to use Vivli's managed access process to deposit clinical research data.</p> <p>Curation Service & Support: Free user support</p> <p>Increased Storage: Contact support@vivli.org</p> <p>Research Environment: May incur additional costs</p> <p>Independent Review Panel: May incur additional costs</p>	<p>Deposit Fee: none</p> <p>Curation Service & Support: Free user support</p> <p>Increased Storage: Contact Zenodo</p> <p>Research Environment: N/A</p> <p>Independent Review Panel: N/A</p>

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Size Limits	<p>2.5GB per file upload default (larger files accommodated on request)</p> <p>2.5TB per user account (Harvard affiliates)</p> <p>1TB per user account (Non-Harvard affiliates)</p> <p>Large data storage support: No limitation</p>	<p>2TB per total dataset package; 10GB per file (recommended)</p>	<p>20GB per published item (e.g., dataset)</p> <p>20GB per file</p> <p>500 files per item</p> <p>50 versions per item</p> <p>500 items per user account</p> <p>Figshare Plus offers up to 5TB of storage per dataset as well as higher limits for individual file sizes and number of files per dataset, subject to additional requirements.</p>	<p>Unlimited files capped at 10GB per dataset</p> <p>Unlimited datasets per user account</p> <p>Institutional users of Digital Commons Data: 100GB per dataset</p>	<p>50GB for projects and child/sub projects (public)</p> <p>5GB for projects and child/sub projects (private)</p> <p>5GB per file upload limit for native OSF Storage</p> <p>There is no limit imposed by OSF for the amount of storage used across add-ons (external storage providers authenticated by the user) connected to a given project.</p>	<p>Up to 4TB of total data</p> <p>Reach out to support@vivli.org for options of datasets greater than 4TB.</p> <p>See the Vivli Share Data webpage for more information</p>	<p>50GB per record</p> <p>100 files max per record</p> <p>One-time quota up to 200GB for a single record</p> <p>Fair usage limits apply (i.e., not unlimited 50GB datasets)</p> <p>See this Zenodo FAQ for more information</p>
Licensing Options	<p>The following licenses are available:</p> <p>CC0 1.0 (repository default)</p> <p>CC BY 4.0</p> <p>CC BY-NC 4.0</p> <p>CC BY-NC-ND 4.0</p> <p>CC BY-NC-SA 4.0</p> <p>CC BY-ND 4.0</p> <p>CC BY-SA 4.0</p> <p>PDDL-1.0</p> <p>ODC-By 1.0</p> <p>ODbL 1.0</p> <p>OGL UK 3.0</p> <p>MIT</p> <p>Custom Dataset Terms</p>	<p>The following licenses are available:</p> <p>CC0</p> <p>CCBY (via Zenodo integration)</p> <p>Additional license options are available for supplemental files (via Zenodo integration) using the SPDX list of licenses.</p>	<p>The following licenses are available:</p> <p>CC0</p> <p>CC-BY 4.0</p> <p>MIT</p> <p>GPL</p> <p>GPL 2.0+</p> <p>GPL 3.0+</p> <p>Apache 2.0</p> <p>Figshare Plus offers additional licenses including:</p> <p>CC BY-SA 4.0</p> <p>CC BY-ND 4.0</p> <p>CC BY-NC 4.0</p> <p>CC BY-NC-SA 4.0</p> <p>CC BY-NC-ND 4.0</p> <p>BSD 3-Clause</p> <p>MPL-2.0</p> <p>CDLA-Sharing-1.0</p>	<p>The following licenses are available:</p> <p>CC0 (no restrictions)</p> <p>CC BY 4.0</p> <p>CC BY NC 3.0</p> <p>MIT</p> <p>Apache 2.0</p> <p>BSD 3-Clause</p> <p>BSD 2-Clause</p> <p>GPL v3</p> <p>GPL v2</p> <p>LGPL</p> <p>MPL-2.0</p> <p>CeCILL</p> <p>CeCILL-B</p> <p>CERN OHL</p> <p>TAPR OHL</p>	<p>The following licenses are available:</p> <p>'No license' is a copyright license for the project authors and contributors.</p> <p>CC0 1.0</p> <p>CC-By 4.0</p> <p>CC BY-NC-ND 4.0</p> <p>CC BY-SA 4.0</p> <p>MIT Apache 2.0</p> <p>BSD 2-Clause</p> <p>BSD 3-Clause</p> <p>GPL 3.0</p> <p>GPL 2.0</p> <p>Artistic 2.0</p> <p>Eclipse 1.0</p> <p>LGPL 3.0</p> <p>LGPL 2.1</p> <p>Mozilla 2.0</p> <p>AFL 3.0</p> <p>Other/custom: user defines a license in a .txt file and uploads to the project (not available on registrations or collections)</p>	<p>To access data your institution needs to agree to sign a Data Use Agreement specifying terms for use and re-use of the data.</p> <p>To share data, your institution will need to agree to a Data Contribution Agreement.</p>	<p>All metadata licensed CC0</p> <p>Record licenses can be chosen from the SPDX list or a custom license can be added.</p> <p>See the Zenodo documentation for more information.</p>

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Free Access to Data	Free access to published datasets including files and metadata	Free access to published datasets including files and metadata	Free access to published datasets including files and metadata All metadata published on Figshare.com are available free of restriction under the CC0 license.	Metadata is licensed CC0. Free access to published datasets including files and metadata Long-term access in the event of cease of operations granted by DANS Free access to archived datasets is provided in perpetuity.	Public data and metadata are indexed and available for download by anyone. Open public API to support broad indexing Reuse is based on a contributor-provided license.	Free access to data that is downloadable There is a no charge period for data that is only accessible in a research environment. Costs are incurred after the no charge period ends.	Free access to published datasets including files and metadata
Preservation	Harvard University supports permanent bit-level preservation of all materials directly deposited in the Harvard Dataverse.	Published datasets are stored, protected, and preserved indefinitely. Backups are stored in three geographically distinct locations.	Figshare has a sustainable business model to support long term access to the repository. Automatic backups of all figshare.com data files and metadata are performed nightly, directly to Figshare-managed Amazon Web Service (AWS) S3 buckets. AWS S3 versioning allows for the immediate restore of content in case of deletion of a file.	Published datasets are archived with Data Archiving and Network Services (DANS) to preserve your data over the long term. DANS is a long-term archiving provider, which is an institute of the Dutch Academy KNAW, and of the Netherlands' national research council, NWO. We contract with DANS to archive all valid published datasets in perpetuity. The agreement ensures that the DOIs we provide for datasets will always resolve to a web page, where the dataset metadata and files will be available. Data archived at DANS is backed up and stored in three locations for redundancy.	Full OSF data file and metadata backups are performed twice daily, managed by Google Cloud Services. We have a partnership with Internet Archive for long-term preservation, as well as a 250k USD preservation fund to support read-only access to data even in the scenario of COS ceasing operations.	Vivli preserves the data for its useful lifetime, which we define as a minimum of 10 years, unless there is a different contractual lifespan. On an ongoing basis, Vivli evaluates its data holdings with regard to maintaining access and reserves the right to discontinue the distribution of a data collections when deemed appropriate.	Bit-level preservation See the Zenodo policies and Zenodo infrastructure pages for more information.

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Retention Policy	All content on Harvard Dataverse will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. Large data deposits are retained for a minimum period of 6 years.	All published content on Dryad will be retained for the lifetime of the repository.	All content on Figshare will be retained for the lifetime of the repository.	User Profile/Activity are retained for 6 years from the user's last active date. Datasets and metadata are retained indefinitely, or for the lifetime of the dataset.	Files are stored in multiple locations and across various media types on Google Cloud. All data is retained for the lifetime of the repository.	Anonymized clinical trial participant data is hosted on the Microsoft Azure Cloud, which provides a secure and scalable infrastructure with advanced security features and compliance certifications. Azure's global infrastructure enables Vivli to implement data redundancy and backup strategies, ensuring that data is protected and accessible over time. For more information, visit this link .	Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository, which is tied to the lifetime of the host laboratory, CERN. Currently, CERN has an experimental program defined for at least the next 20 years.
Data Storage Location	United States and geographically disparate locations	United States Germany	Ireland Germany	Ireland	United States Germany Canada Australia	United States	CERN
Version Support	Yes More information in the Dataverse User Guides	Yes (permanent DOIs) More information available here	Yes More information is available here	Yes Including version comparison , to easily see what has changed from version to version	Yes, for all files utilizing OSF Storage This is available when supported for integrated storage providers . All versions are maintained. Each version is given a unique DOI for preprints .	Yes (updated DOIs) More information here	Yes See the Zenodo documentation and Zenodo policies for more information.
Metadata							
Metadata Schemas	CroissantML DataCite Data Documentation Initiative Codebook Dublin Core OpenAIRE Open Archives Initiative Object Reuse and Exchange (OAI-ORE) Schema.org	DataCite Plus additional (optional) metadata Schema.org	DataCite Schema.org	DataCite Dublin Core Schema.org	Crossref (for preprints) DataCite Schema.org Five specialized community schemas made available via CEDAR	DataCite	DataCite Additional fields for software, publishing information, conferences, and domain-specific fields (currently supporting DarwinCore and Audiovisual Core)

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Formats Supported for Metadata Export	JSON JSON-LD XML	CSV JSON	JSON XML	JSON XML XML formats are defined in the OAI-PMH repository with JSON provided via API documentation .	JSON JSON-LD	Forthcoming	BibTeX Citation File Format Citation Style Language Codemeta CSV DataCite JSON DataCite XML DCAT Dublin Core XML GeoJSON JSON JSON-LD (Schema.org) MARCXML
Supported Research Subject Area Taxonomy	A non-standard list of 13 subjects and an 'Other' option User-selected controlled vocabulary support for keywords fields	Primary research domains are drawn from the OECD Fields of Science and Technology classification.	ANZSRC 2020 Fields of Research (FoR) codes	Omniscience taxonomy for subject categories and keywords Additional custom vocabularies can be loaded on the institutional version.	Bepress, with custom additions for community providers	Cochrane Linked Data Vocabulary	European Science Vocabulary (EuroSciVoc) GEMET (General Multilingual Environmental Thesaurus) Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) NVS (NERC Vocabulary Server)
Persistent Identifiers and Interoperability							
Persistent Unique Identifiers for Records	DataCite DOI	DataCite DOI	DataCite DOI	DataCite DOI	DataCite DOI (Projects and Registrations/ archived data) Crossref DOIs (preprints)	DataCite DOI	DataCite DOI
Author Identifiers	DAI GND ISNI LCNA ORCID ResearcherID Scopus Author ID VIAF	ORCID	ORCID	Mendeley ID ORCID Scopus Author ID	ORCID ResearcherID	ORCID	GND ISNI ORCID

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Author Organization Affiliation	Yes ROR	Yes ROR	ROR Forthcoming in 2025	Yes ROR	Yes ROR	Yes ROR	Yes European Directory of Marine Organizations (EDMO) ROR
Grant ID(s)	Yes Free text	Yes	Yes Dimensions search by award title or ID, or via free text	Yes Grant IDs are captured from user as text.	Yes Grant IDs are captured from user as text.	Yes	Yes Auto-completion from an internal grant database based on OpenAIRE Graph (~4M grants) with additional information such as start/end dates and funding program
Funder ID(s)	Yes	Yes ROR	Yes ROR	Yes CrossRef ROR	Yes Crossref Funder Registry API	Yes ROR	Yes ROR
Links to Related Material	Yes Related journal articles and other text-based publications can be specified with PIDs such as DOIs and the relationTypes 'IsCitedBy', 'Cites', 'IsSupplementTo', 'IsSupplementedBy', 'IsReferencedBy', and 'References'. Other research objects can be specified in other free text fields.	Yes Dataset Data Management Sharing Plan (DMSP) Preprint Primary research article Software Supplementary Material	Yes Related publications can be specified with a title, identifier (e.g., DOI, URL), and relationship type.	Yes DataCite and Scholix relation types Datasets can be related to any URL with relationships 'cites', 'is source of', 'compiles', and 'derives from'.	Yes Preprints link to related peer-reviewed publications using Crossref 'isPreprint of', as well as related study plans and data. Registrations can associate with papers and other data/code/ materials using DataCite relation types . Projects can be associated with study plans and preprints.	Yes Related materials may be specified in 'Additional Notes' field of study posting.	Yes All types (data, event, image, lesson, model, other, physical object, poster, presentation, publication, software, video/audio, workflow) 'Alternate Identifiers' and 'Related Works' fields are available DataCite relation types are supported.

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Code Repository Integrations for Software Publishing	Yes GitHub integration	Yes Dryad is partnered with Zenodo to offer an option for hosting software files and supplemental information. Since non-data files or previously published files may not always meet the CC0 waiver requirement of Dryad, submitters can choose to upload these files to Zenodo and select a separate license for them during the final stage of submission. Files uploaded as 'Supplemental Information' will automatically be licensed under CC BY. Uploading to Zenodo is entirely optional.	Yes Integrations are available for GitHub, GitLab, and Bitbucket to publish software and code repositories in Figshare.	Yes with semantic links	Yes via GitHub and GitLab integrations	Yes Analytical software is available for use within the research environment.	Yes GitHub integration
Machine Interoperability	FAIR Signposting Globus OAI-PMH REST API SWORD	FAIR Signposting REST API	FAIR Signposting FTPS OAI-PMH REST	FAIR Signposting OAI-PMH	FAIR Signposting JSON-LD embedded in landing pages OAI-PMH REST API	None	FAIR Signposting JSON-LD embedded in landing page OAI-PMH REST API
Usage Statistics and Metrics							
Usage Statistics	Views for select users (via dashboards, on request) Downloads (all users via GUI and API) Data volume (via API only)	Views Downloads Citations	Views Downloads Citations Altmetrics	Views Downloads Citations Altmetrics	Views Downloads (per version) Forks Links Referrer	Views Downloads (study documents) Citations Access of data package Vivli request metrics are also captured.	Views Downloads Citations Data volume
Normalized Usage Statistics and Supported Data Use Metrics	Yes No standard followed	Yes Following Make Data Count and Counter Code of Practice DataCite Usage Tracker	Yes Following Make Data Count and Counter Code of Practice DataCite Usage Tracker	Yes Following Make Data Count standards using the Counter Code Of Practice for Research Data Usage Metrics, DataCite Usage Tracker, and PlumX Metrics	Yes Following Make Data Count and Counter Code of Practice for Research Data Usage Metrics DataCite Usage Tracker	Yes Following Make Data Count and Counter Code of Practice DataCite Usage Tracker	Yes Following Make Data Count and Counter Code of Practice DataCite Usage Tracker

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Access Control							
Embargo	Yes File level	Yes Upon request and confirmation of journal approval	Yes File level and dataset level	Yes File level and dataset level	Yes For registration and archiving	Yes File level and dataset level	Yes Dataset level
Peer Review Access	Yes Preview URLs	Yes Authors can choose to keep datasets private during manuscript peer review. A private, temporary URL will be provided to allow double-anonymized access to the journal office and reviewers. After manuscript acceptance, authors can release the dataset for curation and publication by logging into their Dryad dashboard. More information is available here .	Yes Authors can generate a private link to provide access to a published or unpublished dataset which removes author names and provides access to peer reviewers or editors. This link can be disabled or set to expire. More information is available here .	Yes Allows for peer review and private sharing while a draft dataset is under embargo.	Yes A view only link is available with the ability to anonymize contributor list.	Yes Allows for private access via the Vivli secure research environment	Yes Access is available via private URL or direct share with a specific user. See Zenodo's 'Collaborate and Share' documentation for more information.
Managed Access	Yes Managed access functionality	No	No	Yes Researcher-managed access	Yes Request access and private sharing must be set.	Yes Users must request access to the data for a specific research proposal and all requests must be approved before access is granted through a managed access process.	Yes Managed access by researcher or community curator
Anonymized Human Subject Research Data	Yes The author is responsible for ensuring the data are anonymized. File-level restrictions File-level embargoes	Yes Dryad's team of experienced data curators will assist authors in preparing their data for safe and compliant sharing. The author is responsible for ensuring the data are anonymized. More information is available here .	Yes The author is responsible for ensuring the data are anonymized per Figshare Terms .	Yes The author is responsible for ensuring the data are anonymized.	Yes The author is responsible for ensuring the data are anonymized. See the Terms of Use for more information.	Yes Vivli only accepts anonymized data. Our partners Privacy Analytics and Real Life Sciences offer anonymization services to individuals and organizations who wish to share clinical research data on the Vivli platform.	Yes The author is responsible for ensuring the data are anonymized. See Terms of Use and this Zenodo FAQ for more information.

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Registries and Certification							
FAIRsharing Record	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.t2e1ss	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.wkggtx	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.drtwnh	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.3epmpp	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.g4z879	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.uovQrT	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.wy4egf
re3data Record	https://doi.org/10.17616/R3C880	https://doi.org/10.17616/R34S33	https://doi.org/10.17616/R3PK5R	https://doi.org/10.17616/R3DD11	https://doi.org/10.17616/R3N03T	https://doi.org/10.17616/R3SB9S	https://doi.org/10.17616/R3QP53
RRID Record	https://scicrunch.org/resolver/RRID:SCR_001997	https://scicrunch.org/resolver/RRID:SCR_005910	https://scicrunch.org/resolver/RRID:SCR_004328	https://scicrunch.org/resolver/RRID:SCR_002750	https://scicrunch.org/resolver/RRID:SCR_003238	https://scicrunch.org/resolver/RRID:SCR_018080	https://scicrunch.org/resolver/RRID:SCR_004129
Certification	No	No	Yes ISO 27001	Yes Core Trust Seal via DANS ISO 27001	Yes SOC 2	Yes SOC 2 Type 2	No

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User Support							
<p>Moderation / Quality Assurance (QA)</p>	<p>Automated Moderation: Yes. SPAM filter to prevent publishing of possible spam content. Ingest tools that convert certain files to tabular format and extracts additional metadata (#observations #Variables) and allows for integration with Data Explorer and visualize tools such as previewers</p> <p>Human Moderated: Yes. Post publication review to remove spam, identify any deposits violating sensitive data, possible metadata improvements, and any bugs in the software.</p> <p>Staff Responsible for Moderation: Yes, as described above</p> <p>User Moderation Allowed: Yes</p> <p>See: Harvard Dataverse General Terms of Use</p>	<p>Automated Moderation: Yes. An integration with the Frictionless framework allows for automated data validation, focused on the format and structure of tabular data files, prior to Dryad's curation services. JSON and XML files are also checked for basic file validity. Soon, Dryad will implement an automated check for sensitive data, including human and species data.</p> <p>Human Moderation: Yes. Dryad's curation process helps ensure that future users can easily interpret the data package and efficiently analyze and reuse the data.</p> <p>Staff Responsible for Moderation: Yes. Curators carefully assess submissions for issues related to reusability, provenance, interoperability, and clarity, however, they do not evaluate the scientific accuracy or rigor of the research.</p> <p>User Moderation Allowed: No. Although, any user can contact Dryad's Help Desk to communicate concerns.</p> <p>More information about Dryad's curation and publication process is available here.</p>	<p>Automated Moderation: Yes, Figshare conducts automated MD5 integrity checks on files when they are uploaded and Figshare's default storage, Amazon AWS S3, performs regular, systematic data integrity checks as well. Figshare also runs a semi-automated spam detection process which flags potential spam submissions and blocks domains frequently used to create accounts that publish spam.</p> <p>Human Moderation: Yes</p> <p>Staff Responsible for Moderation: Yes, Figshare admins review the outputs of the semi-automated spam detection process described above and remove confirmed spam items and accounts.</p> <p>User Moderation Allowed: No, although logged in users may submit a support ticket via the report feature to flag content for review and moderation by Figshare staff.</p> <p>More information here</p>	<p>Automated Moderation: Yes</p> <p>Human Moderation: Yes</p> <p>Staff Responsible for Moderation: Yes</p> <p>User Moderation Allowed: Yes, with purchase of institutional repository via Digital Commons Data</p> <p>See our Moderation Policy</p>	<p>Automated Moderation: Yes, content is scanned by several trained anti-spam or malicious content software.</p> <p>Human Moderation: Yes, content flagged by softwares are human moderated by COS staff</p> <p>Staff Responsible for Moderation: Yes</p> <p>User Moderation Allowed: though any user or reader may submit a support ticket to the OSF Support Center. Review and appeals procedures are publicly available.</p>	<p>Automated Moderation: No</p> <p>Human Moderation: No</p> <p>Staff Responsible for Moderation: No</p> <p>User Moderation Allowed: No</p>	<p>Automated Moderation: Yes, spam and basic content moderation</p> <p>Human Moderation: Yes, spam and basic content moderation</p> <p>See Zenodo's FAQs on safelisting and spam for more information.</p> <p>Staff Responsible for Moderation: Yes, further curation and moderation is applied to specific Zenodo communities (e.g., EU Open Research Repository) including both manual and automated grant validation, user validation, and subject classification.</p> <p>User Moderation Allowed: No</p>

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Curation	Harvard Dataverse is a self-curated data repository. Users can request a free consultation on preparing their data for sharing. The repository also offers Paid Curation Services (including for large data).	Dryad Curators review research metadata, raw data files, and related materials to ensure that the dataset is well-organized, complete, and accessible. Curators liaise with authors to improve data packages by educating them on best practices for data sharing and providing guidance on applying FAIR principles. Learn more about Dryad's curation process here .	Curation is not offered on figshare.com . Datasets on Figshare Plus are curated for metadata quality and completeness to support discovery and reuse.	Curation in the form of creating collections and customization is available for a fee to our Digital Commons Data institutional clients.	All preprints, postprints, or reports are moderated by community moderators or COS staff. More information about the COS moderation policy is available here . OSF registrations, data, and projects may be moderated by community or institutional administrators. Not all submitted files are moderated. Through an enhanced member dashboard, reports, and other tools a member institution administrator can track aggregate analytics, trends, and open practice adoption within the community and relative to peer institutions, as well as contact all affiliates via the OSF. They can also request access to affiliated content with a special curator permission, enabling them to help researchers maintain and enhance their content and metadata.	Vivli offers curation of the study metadata through a process overseen by Cochrane .	Zenodo uses a model of distributed curation for domain experts through the Community feature . This allows domain experts to curate specific areas of Zenodo. Examples include the Biodiversity Literature Repository, which has highly-curated biodiversity data extracted from publications, as well as the EU Open Research Repository in which all content is curated by EU program beneficiaries and a small dedicated team.

TOPIC	DATAVERSE (HARVARD DATAVERSE REPOSITORY)	DRYAD	FIGSHARE	MENDELEY	OSF	VIVLI	ZENODO
<p>Repository Offerings to Support Institutions</p>	<p>The Dataverse Project is an open source repository building software available to the world wide research data sharing community.</p> <p>The Harvard Dataverse is a Global Dataverse Community Consortium member supporting institutional repositories with data sharing needs.</p> <p>The Harvard Dataverse Repository is an endowed repository that allows both non-Harvard and Harvard affiliates to use its services. All users have access to consultation services, paid curation services, and paid large data support services. Institutions and organizations can select to install the software and build their own institutional repository based on DV.</p> <p>Institutions and organizations can consult with our team for any curation needs, whether using HDV or with their own DV Installation. They can pay for larger storage options within HDV, curation services such as collection and dataset creation, and file upload and long-term maintenance of their collection within HDV. DV/HDV-supported institutions get access to our Google community, Zulip, and our network of working groups and interest groups free of charge.</p> <p>More information here</p>	<p>Institutions and funders become part of the Dryad community to support researchers who use Dryad for data sharing, while also benefiting from an efficient, ready-made solution for curating, publishing, sharing, and preserving research data produced through their funding.</p> <p>Societies, research organizations, and publishers join Dryad to improve their services for authors by offering data publishing support, promoting research integrity, facilitating peer review, and helping to shape best practices for data sharing and reuse.</p> <p>Dryad connects seamlessly to submission and publication workflows via API or email-based integration. Members have hands-on access to a dashboard displaying activity for each dataset, from submission through curation and publication, and including responsibility for payment. Institutions may view data for all affiliated researchers while publishers view all data coming through in association with their journals.</p> <p>Learn more about partnering with Dryad here.</p>	<p>Figshare supports both institutional data repositories and traditional institutional repositories to give institutions more oversight and control over their research outputs. Building on everything available in figshare.com, the institutional version of Figshare includes more configuration options along with tools and features for managing records and working with papers, theses, and data. Delivered via a Software as a Service model, institutions license Figshare software and have access to additional functionality to support funder compliance and repository management. These include but are not limited to a curation workflow, higher file size limits, restricted access options, batch management, and custom metadata and license options.</p> <p>More information here</p>	<p>Digital Commons Data is our Institutional Data Repository and provides tools and storage above and beyond our free Mendeleey Data repository.</p>	<p>OSF Institutions enables administrators of institutional members to capture and preserve research lifecycle data, reports, code, and other materials contributed to OSF that their own repository, if they have one, cannot manage.</p> <p>In addition, OSF allows their researchers to share and organize all the parts of their research process including initial project registration, protocols and data created during analysis, and final dissemination through preprints.</p> <p>Researchers can comply with funder data sharing requirements while keeping their content affiliated with institutional resources.</p> <p>Through an enhanced member dashboard, reports, and other tools, the administrator can track aggregate analytics, trends, and open practice adoption within the community relative to peer institutions, as well as contact all affiliates via the OSF.</p> <p>They can also request access to affiliated content with a special curator permission, enabling them to help researchers maintain and enhance their content and metadata.</p>	<p>Vivli offers a range of services for institutions as part of their membership to support effective data sharing including:</p> <p>Master Data Contributor Agreement: A one-time agreement between Vivli and the institution to cover all studies shared by the institution's investigators</p> <p>Platform Customization: Tailored features on the Vivli platform to meet the institution's specific data-sharing needs</p> <p>Independent Review Panel (IRP): Institutions can either use their own centralized IRP to review data access requests or rely on Vivli's IRP for decision-making.</p> <p>Data Anonymization Support: Special vendor pricing for anonymizing datasets to facilitate compliance with privacy standards</p> <p>Training and Support: Comprehensive training for institutions and direct support for researchers to archive data and meet funder mandates</p> <p>Custom Reports: Bespoke reports for institutions and detailed summaries for investigators about shared data and its re-use</p>	<p>The Zenodo-community feature allows institutions to set up a dedicated area within Zenodo. Support is limited to Zenodo's free service offering.</p> <p>The software engine behind Zenodo, InvenioRDM, is available for institutions worldwide and can be customized to your institutional or domain-specific needs, staying close to Zenodo's simple and seamless user experience.</p> <p>Stay up to date with the Zenodo blog or learn more about the InvenioRDM open source project.</p>